

Magnetite nanoplates decorated on anodized aluminum oxide nanofibers as a novel adsorbent for efficient removal of As (III)

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Abstract

In this study, arsenic as an environmental top ranked hazardous substance was efficiently removed by a novel adsorbent fabricated by magnetite Fe₃O₄ nanoplates decorated on anodized aluminum oxide (AAO) nanofibers. AAO nanofibers were prepared by anodic polarization method and then, Fe₃O₄ nanoplates were grown on AAO-based substrate by hydrothermal method. Morphology of the fabricated adsorbents was characterized by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and their crystallinity was studied by x-ray diffraction (XRD). Arsenic (III) removal potential of the proposed adsorbent from contaminated water samples were investigated by the determination of As(III) amounts in the samples by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) before and after adsorption process. The results showed that without pre- and post-treatment such as pH adjustment, As(III) was removed effectively from contaminated water samples by using the proposed adsorbent. AAO/Fe₃O₄ sorbent showed excellent ability to remove 0.1 mgL⁻¹ As(III) from water samples up to 96%

uptake. Freundlich adsorption isotherm model was used to interpret the As(III) adsorption on proposed sorbent. The Freundlich isotherm parameters, n and k_F , were obtained to be 2.2 and 10.2, respectively, representing the high affinity of proposed adsorbent for arsenic removal.

Keywords: Magnetite Fe₃O₄ nanoplates, Anodized aluminum oxide nanofibers, Arsenic removal, Water samples

Introduction

Arsenic is an important element that has impacts on public health, commercial interests, the environment, water and geopolitics. Arsenic (As) is a common environmental contaminant found naturally in groundwater. It is reported that As contaminated groundwater has been identified as serious threats in parts of world such as Bangladesh, Argentina, China, Taiwan, United States etc. and it seems that more than 100 million people of the world may be at risk from arsenic-contaminated water . The presence of As in groundwater is largely the result of minerals dissolving from rocks and soils. As a new arsenic rule in drinking water, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) lowered the maximum concentration level of allowed As content in water systems from 50 ng/mL to 10 ng/mL at 2002 (US EPA 2002). Among the natural occurring worldwide of As, its compounds have been used widespread as a pigment (copper acetoarsenite, known as

Paris green), medicinal agent (arsenic trioxide), insecticide (copper arsenite), herbicide (disodium methane arsonate) and as a well-known semiconductor material (gallium arsenide). The inorganic As compounds are very toxic and should be removed from water and food.

In general, the toxicity of arsenic follows the order: Inorganic As (III) species > Organic As (III) species > Inorganic As (V) species > Organic As (V) species > Elemental Arsenic.

For the removal of As from water resources, different techniques have been developed including membrane-filtration, oxidation-precipitation, coagulation/electro-coagulation and adsorption processes. Among these methods, adsorption techniques using nanosorbents have their unique advantages including high ability for the treatment of As-rich water contents due to having high active sites in surface, simplicity in performance and operation, low recurring cost and production of less sludge volume. As another advantage of the adsorption technique is the fact that the spent arsenic adsorbents are a non-toxic solid waste and would not be characterized as hazardous waste (US EPA 2000) and can be advantageously utilized as a component for manufacturing bricks thus encapsulating arsenic.

Iron oxides are effective owing to high affinity between iron oxides and arsenic species. Consequently, up to now, various nanocomposites of zero-valent iron or iron oxides/hydroxides such as polycrystalline iron oxide hydroxide nanoparticle Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and magnetic Fe-hydrotalcite have been developed. As removal abilities of aluminum oxide nanocomposites have been widely investigated. The main reason of

these studies is to increase the removal efficiency as well as decrease the time necessary for efficient As removal.

This study aims to develop a new type of adsorbent based on anodized aluminum oxide on which magnetite Fe_3O_4 nanoplates were decorated as an effective adsorbent for removing As(III) from contaminated water samples. Anodization as a simple and inexpensive electrochemical method was used to fabricate alumina nanofibers with high surface area on the surface of Al sheet. To the best of our knowledge, there is not any report on As removal by the proposed AAO-based adsorbent. Arsenic contact time with adsorbent, initial As concentration, the effect of pH of solution, and the effect of the presence of some co-existing anions such as phosphate ion on As(III) removal was studied. Freundlich adsorption isotherm model was used to interpret the adsorption data and the isotherm parameters were calculated.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and apparatus

As(III) stock solution of $100.0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of As_2O_3 in 100-mL volumetric flask in a small volume of NaOH (0.1 M) solution and diluting with DI water to the mark. The pH of this solution was adjusted to pH 7.0 by adding droplets of 0.1 M HCl solution. All diluted As(III) solutions including subsequent working standard solutions and As(III) solutions in adsorption experiments were prepared from the stock solution by exact dilution. For arsenic measurements, inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES, Thermo Scientific) was used. The

surface topography of AAO films was studied using Thermo Microscope Autoprobe CP-Research atomic force microscopy (AFM) and the surface morphology of the samples was characterized by using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, ZEISS-Sigma VP, Germany). Infrared spectra of the samples were conducted by FT-IR spectrometer (Bruker, Germany). X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis with CoK_α radiation source was employed to determine the crystallinity of the samples.

Synthesis of alumina nanofibers by anodization method

Anodized aluminum oxide (AAO) nanofibers were fabricated via one-step anodization of aluminum (Al) sheet (99.9% purity, 0.4 mm thickness, 10×30 mm). Before anodization process, Al sheet was degreased with acetone and ethanol for two times. Then, it was electropolished in a 1:4 mixture of HClO_4 and ethanol by applying 20 V anodic potential for 1 min. The sample was washed with ethanol and deionized water and dried in air. Because of the process, Al sheet with an apparent mirror-like and shiny was obtained. Anodization process was performed in an unstirred oxalic acid solution (0.3 M) at a constant anodic potential of 45 ± 1 V for 60 min in a two-electrode electrochemical system including Al sheet as anode and stainless steel sheet as cathode.

Hydrothermal deposition of magnetite Fe_3O_4 nanoplates

$\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{CO}$ was used as precursors. At first, 4.0 mL of Fe(III) solution and 4.0 mL of urea with various concentrations were mixed in a beaker. Then, AAO substrate was vertically placed into a Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and the mixture was transferred into autoclave and hydrothermally treated at 120 °C for different times (Table 1).

As(III) removal by alumina-based nanosorbent

100.0 mL of each of working As(III) solution with desired concentration was taken in 250-ml beaker and the adsorbent (**Table 1**, ANS-1 to ANS-7) was immersed into the solution vertically. Then, the working solution was magnetically stirred with the speed of 500 rpm. After the desired adsorption times, 2.0 mL of the solution were taken out of the vessel and analyzed for residual As concentration by ICP-OES at the emission wavelength of 189.0 nm under optimized experimental conditions.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of anodized aluminum oxide nanofibers

AAO nanofibers were fabricated via one-step anodization of Al sheet in an unstirred oxalic acid solution (0.3 M) under the applied constant anodic potential of 45 V for 60 min. Usually, the growth of oxide film on the metallic substrate by applying constant anodic potential can be monitored by recording the current-time behavior. During the anodization process, the current density (j) was changed with time as depicted in **Fig. S1** (Supplementary data). **Fig. 1** (A) shows the SEM image of alumina nanotubes grown by the anodization method in a stirred oxalic acid (0.3 M) solution in 10°C for 20 min. Under these conditions, AAO nanotube arrays were obtained, as reported by the others (Zhao et al. 2005, Han et al. 2011). However, under unstirred conditions and at room temperature ($T=25\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for 60 min, the oxidation/solvation rate of pore mouth of nanotube walls began to increase and the formation rate (growth rate) of oxide layer decreased, and as **Fig. 1** (B) shows, AAO nanofibers with high surface area were formed.

The inset of **Fig. 1** (B) shows the formation of dense clusters of nanofibers synthesized under the proposed experimental conditions. The nanofibers are on the order of 40 to 50 nm in diameter and several microns long. AAO nanofibers with increased surface roughness are quite appropriate for adsorption applications of AAO-based nanosorbents. So, in further studies, AAO nanofibers were fabricated under the experimental conditions including applied anodic potential of +45 V, unstirred solution of 0.3 M oxalic acid for 60 min at room temperature.

Fig. 1

Fabrication and characterization of magnetite Fe₃O₄ nanoplates grown

For the growth of Fe₃O₄ on AAO nanofibers, hydrothermal method was used under various conditions including different concentrations of Fe³⁺ and urea, and different hydrothermal reaction times at 120 °C (**Table 1**). Fig. 2 (A) to (D) shows the FE-SEM images of the samples. According to the SEM images, the morphology of Fe₃O₄ nanoplates is not affected considerably by the precursor concentrations. The increase in hydrothermal reaction temperature (from 120°C to 180°C) did not affect the morphology of the samples (**Fig. S3**). The elemental analysis of the sample layers by energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) technique confirmed Al, Fe and oxygen elements (**Fig. S4**).

Fig. 2

Fig. 3 shows the XRD pattern of Fe₃O₄-coated AAO nanofibers (sample ANS-5). The diffraction peaks of aluminum substrate have been shown in XRD pattern. Because of the amorphous structure of AAO fabricated by anodization process (Poinern et al. 2011), there is not any corresponding peak in XRD pattern. The diffraction peaks of Fe₃O₄ reveal the nanocrystalline nature of the sample and match with the crystal phase of magnetite Fe₃O₄ (JCPDS No. 894319, 19-0629). The intensive peaks corresponding to the substrate suppress the diffraction peaks of Fe₃O₄ on the substrate. In addition, these diffraction peaks are broadened owing to small crystallite size of Fe₃O₄. According to Scherrer's equation, the mean grain size of crystallites was obtained to be 27.3 nm.

Fig. 3

Infrared spectra of Fe₃O₄-coated AAO sample is shown in **Fig. 4**. The characteristic absorption bands of the Fe–O bond for bulk Fe₃O₄ are around 375 cm⁻¹ and 570 cm⁻¹, due to the Fe–O stretching mode of the tetrahedral and octahedral sites. In Fe₃O₄ nanoplates, however, these peaks were shifted to 480 cm⁻¹ and 633 cm⁻¹, respectively. The blue-shift of these absorption bands can be attributed to the effect of the finite size of nanoplates (Ma et al. 2003, Ngo et al. 2010). The bands at 1649 cm⁻¹ and 3300 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the H–O–H bending and O–H stretching modes of the adsorbed water molecules on the surface of the sample.

Fig. 4

Arsenic adsorption on Fe₃O₄ nanoplate-coated nanofibers

The effect of contact time

Fig. 5 and **Table 2** show the effect of time of the adsorption process on As(III) removal by ANS-5 nanosorbent at neutral pH at initial concentrations of 0.1 mgL⁻¹ and 1.0 mgL⁻¹ of As(III). The results show a significant removal of As(III) with the increase in contact time. In the beginning, the uptake rate of As(III) is faster compared to the subsequent slower uptake rate, due to the availability of more active surface sites of Fe₃O₄ to the adsorbate in solution. At equilibrium, the removal efficiencies of As(III) at the initial concentrations of 0.1 mgL⁻¹ and 1.0 mgL⁻¹ were 96.0% and 94.5%, respectively. The adsorption equilibrium was achieved in almost 240 min. As **Fig. 5** shows, the adsorption reached equilibrium quickly and the adsorption rate was considerably fast in the first contact time of about 100 min, and few changes were observed from 100 to 240 min indicating that the adsorption of As(III) on ANS-5 nanosorbent was mainly attributed to the chemical sorption or electrostatic interaction between As(III) and sorbent.

Fig. 6

The results are shown in **Fig. 6** and **Table 3**. As the results show, among the adsorbents studied, ANS-5 sample has highest As(III) removal efficiency. In addition, all samples have lower As removal potential by higher initial As(III) concentration (1.0 mgL⁻¹) in comparison with lower one (0.1 mgL⁻¹), due to the saturation of available active surface sites of Fe₃O₄ to the adsorbate in solution containing higher As amounts. Due to the electron deficiency at the surface, Al₂O₃ has strong affinity for the target anions and thus

it was extensively used as adsorbent for the removal of arsenic species (Patra et al. 2012, Han et al. 2013).

Arsenic removal experiments were done under the various pH values of As(III) solution (**Fig. 7**). In acidic media, the removal efficiencies are low. To understand the As(III) adsorption mechanism, pH of zero point charge (pH_{ZPC}) of ANS-5 was determined describing the condition that the electrical charge density on surface is zero. The pH_{ZPC} of ANS-5 was 5.2, below which the surface of sorbent is positively charged and above this amount, the surface of sorbent is negatively charged. On the other hand, the speciation diagram of Arsenite shows that below pH of ~ 8 , the main species is non-charged H_3AsO_3 and above which the anionic species of As(III) are dominant. In addition, in acidic media, the solubility of iron oxide nanosheet causes the loss of material, as confirmed by the determination of iron content of acidic adsorbate solution after removal process.

Fig. 7

The effect of competing anions

The effect of some co-existing anions such as, phosphate and carbonate ions on arsenic adsorption by different ANS samples was examined. In the presence of phosphate ions, the removal efficiency of the samples greatly degrades, but the effect of carbonate anion is not significant (**Table 3**). The significant interference of phosphate ions on As(III) sorption is mainly due to its electrostatic attraction to the adsorbent surface at neutral media. The most abundant anions present in natural water such as chloride and nitrate

ions even at high concentrations did not show deterioration effect on the adsorption of As(III) on the adsorbent sample.

The feasibility of the fabricated ANS-5 sample to remove As(III) from real water samples was tested by using tap water. 100.0 mL of the tap water sample spiked with 0.1 mgL^{-1} As(III) solution was taken in 250-ml beaker and ANS-51 sorbent was immersed into the solution vertically. The results showed that $95 \pm 2\%$ ($n=3$) of the spiked As(III) was removed from the water samples without any pre- and post-treatment such as pH adjustment.

Adsorption isotherm

Fig. 8 demonstrates the As(III) equilibrium adsorption isotherm obtained at near neutral pH environment. As it is clear, the plot of $\log q_e$ vs $\log C_e$ for various initial As(III) concentrations is found to be linear, indicating the applicability of the classical adsorption isotherm to this adsorbate-adsorbent system. From the intercept and the slope of plot, the parameters n and k_F were obtained to be 2.2 and 10.2, respectively. The higher value for k_F indicates the high affinity for arsenic and high adsorbent loading that can be achieved, and n values between 1 and 10 indicate the favorable adsorption.

Table 4 presents Freundlich constants, i.e. k_F and n for As(III) adsorption by the proposed magnetite $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{AAO}$ thin film and other adsorbents reported previously. From the data obtained in As removal by using $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{AAO}$ nanosorbent, it is clear that the

proposed sorbent is very useful adsorbent for arsenic uptake from contaminated water samples.

Fig. 8

Conclusion

A simple two-step method was proposed for the fabrication of AAO-based nanosorbent for arsenic removal from contaminated water samples in neutral media. All of the experimental conditions were optimized for getting satisfactory results. The results showed that without pre- and post-treatment of the water samples such as pH adjustment, As(III) can be effectively removed by Fe₃O₄/AAO nanosorbent. There is not requiring the separation of adsorbent material from the adsorbate solution by filtration. This is the main advantage of proposed nanosorbent. The Freundlich isotherm was fitted to the experimental data to interpret the nature of adsorption mechanism. n and k_F are obtained to be 2.2 and 10.2, representing the high affinity of proposed nanosorbent for As(III) removal.

Appendix: Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this Manuscript has been attached.

Figure Captions

Fig. 1. SEM images of (A) alumina nanotube arrays fabricated under applied anodic potential of 45 V in a stirred oxalic acid solution (0.3 M) in 10°C for 20 min, and (B) alumina nanofibers fabricated under applied anodic potential of 45 V in an unstirred oxalic acid solution (0.3 M) at room temperature for 60 min.

Fig. 2. FE-SEM micrographs of Fe₃O₄ decorated AAO samples. (A) ANS-2, (B) ANS-5, (C) ANS-6, (D) ANS-7. The hydrothermal reaction conditions for the fabrication of samples are depicted in Table 1.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of magnetite Fe₃O₄/AAO sample.

Fig. 4. IR spectra of Fe₃O₄ nanoplates.

Fig. 5. The effect of contact time on As(III) removal by ANS-5 adsorbent at neutral pH and at the initial As(III) concentrations of 0.1 mg/L (◆) and 1.0 mg/L (■).

Fig. 6. %As(III) removal efficiency by all ANS adsorbent samples at neutral pH and at the initial As(III) concentration of 0.1 mg/L.

Fig. 7. The effect of pH on As(III) removal using ANS-5 adsorbent at the initial As(III) concentrations of 0.1 mg/L (◆) and 1.0 mg/L (■). The pH values are the initial values.

Fig. 8. Freundlich adsorption isotherm for As(III) adsorption on ANS-5 adsorbent.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Tables

Table 1. List of experimental conditions for the growth of magnetite Fe₃O₄ nanoplates on AAO nanofibers in different adsorbent samples.

Adsorbent	Fe ³⁺ concentration (M)	Urea concentration (M)	Hydrothermal reaction time (h)
ANS-1	9.0×10 ⁻⁴	9.0×10 ⁻⁴	12
ANS-2	2.5×10 ⁻⁴	1.25×10 ⁻²	12
ANS-3	1.0×10 ⁻²	5.0×10 ⁻²	4
ANS-4	1.0×10 ⁻²	5.0×10 ⁻²	8
ANS-5	1.0×10 ⁻²	5.0×10 ⁻²	12
ANS-6	1.0×10 ⁻²	5.0×10 ⁻²	24
ANS-7	4.0×10 ⁻²	2.0×10 ⁻¹	12

Table 2. %As (III) removal efficiency of ANS-5 adsorbent with the initial As(III) concentrations of 0.1 mg/L and 1.0 mg/L.

Contact time (min)	%As(III) removal* (average±SD, n=3)	%As(III) removal** (average±SD, n=3)
0	0	0
15	40.0±3.5	34.0±2.3
30	73.3±2.8	62.4±2.7
60	82.5±2.1	78.6±1.8
100	92.0±2.4	86.0±1.4
240	96.0±1.8	94.5±0.9

*The initial concentration of As(III) was 0.1 mg/L.

**The initial concentration of As(III) was 1.0 mg/L.

Table 3. The effect of competing anions in As(III) removal at pH 7.0 at the equilibrium time of 240 min.

Adsorbent	%As(III) removal*			%As(III) removal**		
	-	Phosphate ion (0.01 M)	Carbonate ion (0.02 M)	-	Phosphate ion (0.01 M)	Carbonate ion (0.02 M)
ANS-1	56.0	27.5	53.2	42.5	25.2	39.0
ANS-2	72.0	38.0	69.0	65.0	26.1	61.4
ANS-3	89.8	46.0	83.5	83.2	47.5	74.5
ANS-4	94.1	52.0	87.1	91.8	37.0	86.2
ANS-5	96.0	51.6	91.0	94.5	43.4	91.6
ANS-6	92.5	53.4	85.0	92.0	41.0	86.0
ANS-7	91.0	54.2	83.8	93.0	39.3	84.0

*The initial concentration of As(III) was 0.1 mg/L.

**The initial concentration of As(III) was 1.0 mg/L.

Table 4. Comparison of various adsorbents for As(III) removal from water samples.

Adsorbent	k_F (mg/g)	n	Ref.
Magnetite-maghemite nanoparticles	9.4	2.1	Chowdhury and Yanful 2010
Magnetite	10.0	2.5	Mayo et al. 2007
Aluminium doped manganese copper ferrite polymer	0.85	1.5	Malana et al. 2011
Activated alumina	0.22	2.2	Singh and Pant 2004
Activated alumina grains	1.21	1.53	Lin and Wu 2001
TiO ₂ (Degussa P25) suspension	14.0	1.4	Dutta et al. 2004
TiO ₂ (Hombikat UV100) suspension	13.0	1.8	Dutta et al. 2004
Agglomerated Fe(III)–Al(III) mixed oxide nanoparticles	2.53	1.85	Basu and Ghosh 2011
PES/Fe–Mn binary oxide	55.0	0.10	Gohari et al. 2013
Granular ferric hydroxide	18.0	2.3	Thirunavukkarasu et al. 2003
Nanoscale zero-valent iron	3.50	3.27	Kanel et al. 2005
Ultrafine α -Fe ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles	12.55	2.53	Tang et al. 2011
Magnetite-reduced graphene oxide composite	3.79	2.32	Chandra et al. 2010
Magnetite Fe ₃ O ₄ /AAO	10.2	2.2	This work